

Kinetics of Oxidation of Aromatic Ketones by Manganese(III) Acetate

N. C. KHANDUAL & P. L. NAYAK

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3 and G. M. College, Sambalpur

Received 5 November 1971; revised MSS received 22 March 1972

The kinetics of oxidation of acetophenone and substituted acetophenones by Mn(III) acetate has been studied in 95% (vol/vol) acetic acid. The reaction rate was found to be first order with respect to the oxidant as well as to the organic substrate. The reaction rate is unaffected by Mn(II) ions. The rate decreases with increasing the proportion of water in the reaction mixture. The log k values for different substituted acetophenones were plotted against the σ^+ values with $\rho^+ = 1.0$. The rate of enolisation of acetophenone has been compared with oxidation and a probable mechanism has been suggested in the light of the result.

Oxidation studies by electron transfer reactions have received considerable attention during recent years¹. Waters and co-workers² have found that manganese(III) pyrophosphate oxidises cyclohexanone at a rate equal to the rate of enolisation. This gives evidence that ketones are probably oxidised *via* their enol form. Further Littler³ has pointed out that manganese(III) sulphate oxidises cyclohexanone at a rate faster than its enolisation in acid conditions and has concluded that this one equivalent oxidant attack the ketone rather than the enol form of the substrate. We have reported the oxidation of aromatic ketones by a number of oxidants⁴ and in the present investigation we have studied the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of aromatic ketones by manganese(III) acetate.

The acetophenone and its substituted derivatives were prepared by our previous-method⁵. Acetic acid used is of BDH 'AnalaR' grade. Manganese triacetate was prepared from manganous acetate and potassium permanganate by the method of Dewar⁶.

The rate of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted manganese (III) acetate by iodometric procedure. The procedure adopted in quenching a known volume of the reaction mixture to 25 ml of iodate free potassium iodide solution and the liberated iodine was titrated against sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. The rate constants were computed with an accuracy of 1-2% in duplicate runs.

Stoichiometry and Product Analysis : Reduction of 1 mole of manganese (III) acetate by acetophenone produces 0.24 mole of formaldehyde as estimated by chromotropic acid test⁷. Benzoic acid and formaldehyde were found to be the main product of oxidation. The stoichiometry was calculated to be 4 : 1 ($\Delta\text{Mn(III)}/\Delta$ acetophenone). Thus the overall reaction may be written as :

Dependence of [Ketone] and [Mn^{III}]: The rate of the reaction with respect to the ketone and Mn(III) concentrations are described in Table 1. When the ketone concentration is in excess, the rate at which Mn(III) disappears follows first order rate law. Further, the first order rate constant is found to be independent of the initial concentration of Mn(III) indicating that the order with respect to the oxidant is one (Table 1). The reaction rate increases linearly with increase of ketone concentration.

TABLE 1

Dependence of rate on [Mn(III)] and [Acetophenone]
Temp. 35° [HClO₄] = 1.5 × 10⁻¹(M)

[Acetophenone] × 10 ² M	[Mn(III)] × 10 ³ M	k × 10 ⁵ sec. ⁻¹	$\frac{k \times 10^7}{[\text{Aceto}]}$ in mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹
10	2.0	9.21	
10	2.5	9.33	
10	3.5	9.70	
10	4.0	9.50	
10	4.5	9.31	
10	5.0	9.80	
10	5.5	9.65	
12.50	5.0	12.28	9.982
13.75	5.0	13.30	0.985
15.00	5.0	13.70	0.913
16.25	5.0	15.44	0.948
17.50	5.0	16.05	0.917
18.75	5.0	17.00	0.906

Dependence of [Mn(II)]: The rate of oxidation of acetophenone has been studied in various Mn(II) concentrations. Since Mn(II) has no effect on the reaction indicating that Mn(III) is the only oxidising species.

Effect of solvent on rate: The rate of oxidation of acetophenone by Mn(III) acetate has been studied in various acetic acid : water concentrations. The rate of the reaction was found to be decreased with increase of water content in the reaction mixture. It is assumed that these effects are caused by the hydration of the metal ions. The hydrated ions are less reactive with respect to electron removal owing to the lower oxidation potentials.

Influence of substituents on rate: The oxidation was carried out with various substituted acetophenones (Table 3). The order of reactivity of different substituents are as follows :

The log k values were plotted against Brown's σ^+ values⁸ with $\rho^+ = +1$.

The energy and entropy of activations were calculated by usual methods with an accuracy of ± 0.5 kcal/mole and 0.8 e.u. respectively. A straight line was made between the ΔH^\ddagger versus ΔS^\ddagger values with β , the isokinetic temperature being 475°K signifying that the isokinetic relationship is obeyed in the reaction series⁹.

TABLE 2

Effect of solvent composition on rate

Temp. 35°. $[H^+] = 1.5 \times 10^{-1}M$; $[Mn^{III}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$;

$[Acetophenone] = 12.5 \times 10^{-2}M$

HAOC : H ₂ O (v/v)	$k \times 10^5 \text{ sec.}^{-1}$
95	12.28
90	12.00
85	11.52
80	8.44
70	5.37

TABLE 3

Effect of substituent on rate

$[Acetophenone] = 12.5 \times 10^{-2}M$; $[H^+] = 1.5 \times 10^{-1}M$; $[Mn^{III}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$

Substituents	$k \times 10^5 \text{ sec.}^{-1} \text{ in } ^\circ\text{C}$			E k.cal/ mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	ΔF^\ddagger k.cal/ mole	ΔH^\ddagger k.cal/ mole
	35	40	45				
H	12.28	24.57	47.24	24.96	12.67	23.52	24.34
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -	80.61	130.50	207.30	18.42	14.94	22.41	17.81
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -	8.40	18.50	37.20	25.83	14.59	23.80	25.21
<i>p</i> -Cl-	8.15	17.92	35.71	27.47	9.87	24.89	26.86
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -	7.22	16.45	33.53	28.55	13.10	23.89	27.94
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -	5.37	13.05	29.17	30.67	19.35	12.80	18.73

Enolisation rate: The rate constant for the enolisation of acetophenone in 95% acetic acid (vol/vol) was $17.82 \times 10^{-5} \text{ lit. mole}^{-1} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$, whereas the rate constant for the oxidation of acetophenone by Mn(III) acetate was found to be $90.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ lit. mole}^{-1} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$. Thus the oxidation is faster than enolisation and the oxidation involved the attack on the keto form by Mn(III), which also supports the view of Littler³. Further, the Hammett ρ value for the enolisation has been calculated by Nayak and Rout⁵ to be -0.78 indicating that the oxidation and enolisation are probably operated in different path ways.

Considering all these factors the following mechanism may be suggested

The authors are grateful to the authorities of the Sambalpur University for financial assistance.

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